

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.10 REPORT ON VIRTUAL GALLERIES OF THE VOUCHER SPECIMENS COLLECTION

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DOCUMENT INFO

AUTHORS

Surname	First name	Organization	E-mail
Keklikoglou	Kleoniki	HCMR	keklikoglou@hcmr.gr
Vernadou	Emmanouela	HCMR	e.vernadou@hcmr.gr
Chatzinikolaou	Eva	HCMR	evachatz@hcmr.gr
Filiopoulou	Irene	HCMR	filiop@hcmr.gr

INTERNAL REVIEWERS

Surname	First name	Organization	E-mail
Musco	Luigi	CoNISMa	luigi.musco@unisalento.it
Mohammad	Hasan Dad Ansari	SSSA	hasandadansari.mohammad@santannapisa.it

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Micro-CTvlab (<https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) is a web-based virtual gallery of samples generated using micro-computed tomography (micro-CT), hosted by the Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR). This virtual laboratory was developed within the framework of the LifeWatchGreece ESFRI Research Infrastructure project (<https://www.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) which is the national node of LifeWatch ERIC. Its aim is to support biodiversity and ecosystem research by providing accessible data resources, web services, and Virtual Research Environments (VREs) that enable researchers to explore, analyze, and share biological data efficiently.

The Micro-CTvlab provides 3D specimens annotated with metadata, which can be interactively visualized and accessed through a web-based application ^[1]. During the MAPWORMS project, a Voucher Specimens Collection was created in the Micro-CTvlab to share the project's results and data widely and freely, following the FAIR principles. Notably, the FAIRness status of micro-CT data in the Micro-CTvlab was enriched through the addition of new metadata fields, such as funding, copyright, and citation information. Details of the FAIRification process can be found in ^[2].

This deliverable describes an open virtual collection (the Voucher Specimens collection) of the annelid specimens, available to any potential user through the Micro-CTvLab online repository. Additionally, the micro-CT scans are also accessible through the Micro-CTvlab mobile web application (<https://microctapp.hcmr.gr/>), presented in a more user-friendly format for the general public.

2 VOUCHER SPECIMENS COLLECTION

2.1 MICRO-CT VLAB

A total of 76 micro-CT scans representing 19 marine annelid species collected in the framework of the MAPWORMS project along the Salento Peninsula in Italy, were uploaded to the Micro-CTvlab to create a Voucher Specimens collection dedicated to the MAPWORMS project (Table 1).

The majority of the micro-CT scans correspond to the sipunculan *Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni* and the polychaete *Glycera tridactyla*, as these species were ultimately selected as model organisms for the development of bioinspired soft robots during the project and their future implementation. The other species represent peculiar Annelida belonging both to the unsegmented groups (like *P. stephensoni*) and to groups with armed pharynx (like *G. tridactyla*) which are useful to compare the morho-anatomical evolution of the group. This collection can be accessed through the search filters by selecting "MAPWORMS" from the projects list (Figure 1).

Table 1. List of Annelida species and the number of micro-CT scans uploaded to the Micro-CT vLab for each species.

Species	Annelida taxon	Micro-CT scans
<i>Aspidosiphon (Aspidosiphon) muelleri</i> Diesing, 1851	Sipuncula	1
<i>Compositia costae</i> (Grube, 1840)	Polychaeta	4
<i>Drilonereis filum</i> (Claparède, 1868)	Polychaeta	2
<i>Eunice schizobranchia</i> Claparède, 1870	Polychaeta	2
<i>Eunice vittata</i> (Delle Chiaje, 1828)	Polychaeta	1
<i>Euphrosine foliosa</i> Audouin & H Milne Edwards, 1833	Polychaeta	2
<i>Glycera alba</i> (O.F. Müller, 1776)	Polychaeta	2
<i>Glycera tridactyla</i> Schmarda, 1861	Polychaeta	31
<i>Harmothoe fraserthomsoni</i> McIntosh, 1897	Polychaeta	1
<i>Leodice torquata</i> (Quatrefages, 1866)	Polychaeta	1
<i>Lumbrineris latreilli</i> Audouin & Milne Edwards, 1833	Polychaeta	3
<i>Lysidice margaritacea</i> Claparède, 1868	Polychaeta	1
<i>Marphysa victori</i> Lavesque, Daffe, Bonifácio & Hutchings, 2017	Polychaeta	2
<i>Nephtys</i> sp. Cuvier, 1817	Polychaeta	2
<i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i> (Stephen, 1942)	Sipuncula	13
<i>Phylo foetida</i> (Claparède, 1868)	Polychaeta	3
<i>Platynereis dumerilii</i> (Audouin & Milne Edwards, 1833)	Polychaeta	2
<i>Pterocirrus macroceros</i> (Grube, 1860)	Polychaeta	1
<i>Syllis vittata</i> Grube, 1840	Polychaeta	2

Figure 1. The MAPWORMS Voucher Specimens Collection selected from the projects list in the Micro-CTlab.

Within MAPWORMS collection, by selecting a specific micro-CT dataset, users can explore these “cyber-specimens” through four different tabs (Figure 2). The *General Info* tab provides an overview of the selected dataset. It presents basic information on the scientific name of the scanned specimen, the scope of visualization, and the sample preparation and scanning parameters, along with a series of 3D images (Figure 3).

Figure 2 Micro-CT vLab interface illustrating the different user capabilities, including dataset overview, interactive 3D visualization of a sample, an associated video, and the corresponding metadata.

Sample Category :

Zoology / Annelida

General Info	3D Visualization	Video	Metadata
<p>Scientific Name :</p> <p>SpecimenID :</p> <p>ScanID :</p> <p>3D volume rendering of <i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i></p> <p>Micro-CT was performed to a <i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i> specimen. This sample was fixed in formalin and preserved in ethanol. Specimen was stained with 1% Iodine dissolved in 96% ethanol. Scan was performed with a Skyscan 1172 at a voltage of 50kV and 198µA without filter for a half rotation of 180°. This specimen was scanned at the highest camera resolution with an exposure time of 946ms. This scan was performed for the visualisation of the retractor muscles of this specimen within the framework of MAPWORMS project funded from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046846 . Specimen was provided by Luigi Musco (CONISMA) and scanned by Niki Keklikoglou.</p>			

Figure 3. The General Info tab of a selected micro-CT dataset.

Through the *3D visualization* tab, cross-sectional images of the specimen can be interactively displayed in three orthogonal views (Figure 4A) using the opensource Slice:Drop software (<https://slicedrop.com/>). In addition, by selecting the 3D icon in the volume tab, the specimen can be rendered as an interactive 3D model (Figure 4B). This tool allows users to rotate the specimen and adjust opacity, thresholding parameters and color settings. The dataset is also available for download in .nifti format through the link provided above the frame. Homologous structures, such as muscular layers, jaws etc., as well as their shape and organization among the different scanned species may be easily analyzed and compared.

Figure 4. The 3D Visualization tab, where the dataset can be displayed in A) three orthogonal views and B) as 3D model.

By selecting the *Video* tab, a 3D video of the selected scan is displayed (Figure 5). This video demonstrates both the anatomical and morphological features of the specific annelid specimen.

Figure 5. The Video tab with a preview video of the selected annelid scan.

The *Metadata* tab contains a comprehensive list of metadata related to the specimen, sample preparation, and scanning parameters (Figure 6). During the MAPWORMS project, and in accordance with the project's Data Management Plan (DMP) and Article 17 of the MAPWORMS Grant Agreement, additional metadata fields were introduced. These fields are related to funding information, project name, licensing terms, publication date, dataset citation, and persistent identifiers information. Each dataset uploaded to Micro-CTvlab is assigned a unique identifier, resulting in a unique URL. Within this metadata catalogue, micro-CT images, videos, and datasets can be openly downloaded by any user. The naming conventions for images, videos, and datasets follow the MAPWORMS DMP. Datasets, images, and videos are licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), while the metadata are licensed under the Creative Commons Zero 1.0 Public Domain Dedication (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>). More details about the Micro-CTvlab functionalities can be found in ^[1].

Sample Category : [Zoology / Annelida](#)

General Info | 3D Visualization | Video | **Metadata**

[- Show less metadata](#)

SpecimenID :	1 mCT-01334
ScanID :	1 scan-01640
Sample Category :	1 Zoology / Annelida
Scientific Name :	1 <i>Phascolosoma (Phascolosoma) stephensoni</i>
Scientific Name ID :	1 https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=taxdetails&id=136081
Taxonomic Group :	1 ANNELIDA
Provider Institute :	1 CONISMA
Project :	1 MAPWORMS
Funding :	1 European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
Project Info :	1 MAPWORMS project funded from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101046846
Specimen Provider :	1 Luigi Musco
Published by :	1 Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
Publication Date :	1 Thu, 04/04/2024 - 11:30
Material :	1 soft tissue
Fixation Type :	1 formalin
Preservation Medium :	1 Ethanol
Contrast Enhancement Method :	1 Iodine
Scope of Scan :	1 visualisation of retractor muscles
Scan Date :	1 12/19/2022
Scanned By :	1 Niki Keklikoglou
Sample Holder :	1 blue pipette tip
Scanning Medium :	1 ethanol
Scanned Part :	1 whole specimen
Digital Device Type :	1 SkyScan 1172
Voltage kV :	1 50
Current uA :	1 199
Filter :	1 None
Zoom um :	1 6.89
Camera Resolution :	1 4000
ExposureTime (ms) :	1 946
360 :	1 180°
Random Movement :	1 0
Averaging :	1 3
Oversize Settings :	1 None
Dataset :	1 MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640_v1_20240404.nii.gz (239.29 MB)
Dataset URL :	1 https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89
Micro-CT Images :	1 Download MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640image2_v1_20240404.png (393.43 KB) 1 Download MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640image1_v1_20240404.png (551.78 KB)
Video File :	1 MAPWORMS_HCMR_scan-01640_v1_20240404.mp4 (2.24 MB)
Data Licences :	1 http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Data Owner :	1 Niki Keklikoglou
Citation :	1 Keklikoglou, K., Langeneck, J., Musco, L. (2024). Scan-01640.Micro-CTvlab. https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/node/89

Datasets, images and videos are licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Metadata are licensed under <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>

Figure 6. Comprehensive metadata for the selected micro-CT dataset displayed in the Metadata tab.

2.2 MICRO-CT WEB APP

During the MAPWORMS project, a micro-CT web app (<https://microctapp.hcmr.gr/>) was developed on Wordpress CMS with the use of the Web Apps (PWA) plugin in order to provide online access on the MAPWORMS Voucher Specimen collection in a more user-friendly version. This application can be used not only for research purposes but also by academics and students for educational purposes, as well as by artists and animators for creative work. The application is accessible on mobile devices through any web browser and, once installed on the device, it can function like a native application, allowing users to access and explore the marine annelids easily from their smartphone or tablet (Figure 7).

Figure 7. The Micro-CTVlab web application displayed on A) a smartphone and B) a desktop web browser.

By selecting a specific micro-CT dataset from the *Worms* section, a short overview, 3D images, a related video, and representative metadata are displayed (Figure 8). In addition, below the metadata section, a link to the corresponding dataset in Micro-CTVlab is provided for users who require further information.

Figure 8. Micro-CTvlab web application functionalities.

Details about the micro-CT web app can also be found on the Micro-CTvlab website under the "OUR APP" tab (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Micro-CT web app information displayed in the Micro-CTvlab interface.

REFERENCES

^[1] Keklikoglou K, Faulwetter S, Chatzinikolaou E, Michalakis N, Filiopoulou I, Minadakis N, Panteri E, Perantinos G, Gougousis A, & Arvanitidis C (2016). Micro-CTVlab: A web based virtual gallery of biological specimens using X-ray microtomography (micro-CT). Biodiversity Data Journal 4: e8740. <https://bdj.pensoft.net/article/8740/>

^[2] Mavraki D., & Kekikoglou K. (2024). Applying FAIR principles to Micro-CT data, the case of MAPWORMS project. Proceedings of the 5th International Congress on Applied Ichthyology, Oceanography, and Aquatic Environment, pp. 608–611, <https://hydromedit.gr/>